

Soil Salinity Drives Divergence in Agronomic and Physiological Traits of Bread Wheat Cultivars

Somayyeh RAZZAGHI^{1*} (Orcid ID: 0000-0002-8028-452X)

¹ Erciyes University, Faculty of Agriculture, Department of Soil Science and Plant Nutrition, Kayseri

*Sorumlu yazar (Corresponding author): srazzaghi@erciyes.edu.tr

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Abstract

To investigate the physiological and agronomic traits affecting grain yield of wheat genotypes under saline and non-saline field conditions, an experiment was conducted in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications during the 2018–2019 growing season at the Miandoab Agricultural Research Station, Northwest Iran. The treatments examined in this study comprised seven bread wheat genotypes, including the promising lines MS-91-14, MS-89-12, and MS-89-13, as well as the varieties Ofogh, Mihan, Narin, and Barat. Some physiological and agronomic traits of wheat, such as leaf chlorophyll content, as well as grain yield components like thousand-grain weight, number of grains per spike, number of spikelets per spike, and finally biological yield, grain yield, and harvest index (HI), were measured. The results of the comparison of mean data for the studied traits showed that among all genotypes and cultivars, the Mihan variety had the lowest values for the number of spikes per m², grain yield, biological yield, and leaf chlorophyll. In terms of spike weight, the MS-89-13 genotype exhibited the highest values, whereas for thousand-grain weight, MS-89-12 showed the highest performance. Regarding the number of spikelets per spike, thousand-grain weight, biological yield, and grain yield, the Narin variety outperformed the others. With a grain yield of 4000 kg ha⁻¹ under saline soil conditions, Narin was identified as a soil salinity-tolerant wheat cultivar in this study. Therefore, it can be recommended for cultivation in saline soils to achieve higher grain yields. Among the genotypes, MS-89-13 also demonstrated relatively high grain yield, indicating its suitability for cultivation under saline conditions in this region.

Keywords: Soil salinity stress, yield components, wheat genotypes, grain yield

1.Introduction

Wheat is regarded as the primary crop for feeding more than one-third of the world's population and serves as a staple food in Asia (Shirazi et al., 2001). The number of plant species cultivated mainly for food is relatively small; among them, bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) plays a crucial role in human nutrition due to its wide cultivation area and high yield. With the rapidly growing human population, it is essential to develop new approaches for producing wheat varieties with enhanced traits for sustainable agriculture and mitigating climate change (Razzaghi, 2021). Recent efforts have focused on producing varieties with higher grain yield and suitable technological quality, which are both resistant and tolerant to a wide range of biotic and abiotic stresses (Rezaei & Razzaghi, 2012, 2015). However, given the critical nutritional status of the human population, there is an urgent need to develop wheat varieties that contain more nutrients and improve our health under biotic and abiotic stresses (Razzaghi and Rezaei, 2015). Approximately 25% of the world's agricultural land and 15% of Iran's total agricultural land are affected by soil salinity (Kamkar et al., 2004). Among abiotic stresses, soil salinity is regarded as one of the most significant constraints to crop production worldwide (Debez et al., 2006). Salinity in soil or water, especially in arid and semi-arid regions, can severely limit plant production. Saline soils and the associated stress are among the primary abiotic stresses, negatively affecting metabolic processes and potentially causing plant mortality (Roychoudhury et al., 2008). It is estimated that over 2 million hectares of agricultural land experience annual yield reductions due to high levels of sodium and chloride in the soil, a process known as salinization. Over 20% of irrigable

farmland in arid and semi-arid regions was previously affected by salinity and is still increasing (Mühling and Läuchli, 2003). Saline soil in the world and Iran is constantly expanding due to unsustainable agricultural activities, and these soils are facing various types of salinity problems. Soil salinization is one of the major constraints of intensive agriculture (Mer et al., 2000). High concentrations of salt in soil and water have detrimental effects on seed germination and plant growth (Mujeeb-ur-Rahman and Gul, 2000). The detrimental effects of soil salinity on plant growth can be attributed to the low osmotic potential of soil solution (drought stress), elemental imbalances, specific ion effects (salinity stress), or a combination of these factors (Ashraf and Wu, 1994; Marschner, 2011). All these factors have detrimental effects on plant growth and development at physiological and biochemical levels (Ashraf and Wu, 1994) and at the molecular level (Mansour, 2000; Tester and Davenport, 2003). Salinity stress has a different effect on carbohydrate content. Some researchers have reported the accumulation of carbohydrates in multiple plants under saline conditions (Abdel-Samad and Azooz, 2002; Azooz et al., 2004; Parida et al., 2003). Although previous studies have examined the effects of soil salinity on wheat, there is still a limited understanding of how specific physiological and agronomic traits influence grain yield under soil salinity stress in Azerbaijan Province, northwest Iran, across different wheat genotypes. To address this knowledge gap, the present study investigated these traits with the aim of identifying wheat genotypes tolerant to soil salinity with high grain yield in this region, evaluating the effects of soil salinity on yield components, and determining the

correlations between grain yield and its components under soil salinity stress conditions.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area

The experiment was conducted during the 2018–2019 growing season at the Agricultural Research Station in Miandoab County, northwest Iran (46°05' E longitude and 36°00' N latitude, altitude 1,142 m above sea level) to evaluate the effects of soil under saline and non-saline conditions on the physiological and agronomic traits of bread wheat genotypes and cultivars. Long-term meteorological data indicated that the experimental site in Miandoab County had an average annual rainfall of 280 mm, with long-term average minimum and maximum temperatures of 5°C and approximately 20°C, respectively.

2.2. Physicochemical Characteristics of the Studied Soil

Prior to sowing, soil samples were collected from a depth of 0–30 cm. Soil properties were analyzed with the following standard procedures. Particle size distribution, pH (1:2.5 soil-to-water suspension, using a pH meter, Meterohm 691), electrical conductivity (EC) (using an EC meter (Jenway model 4310)), and calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) content were determined according to Bauyoucos (1954), McLean (1965), Black et al. (1983), and Allison and Moodie (1965), respectively. Soil organic carbon (SOC) was assessed using the Walkley–Black method (Walkley and Black, 1934). Available phosphorus (P), potassium (K), and micronutrients such as iron (Fe) and zinc (Zn) were analyzed using the procedures of Olsen (1954), Carson (1980), and Lindsay and Norvell (1978), respectively (Table 1). In the saline soil site, the soil exhibited a silty clay texture, an electrical conductivity of 11.1 dS m⁻¹, and a pH of 9.

Table 1. Soil physical and chemical properties at experimental sites

Soil properties	Saline soil	Non-Saline Soil
EC (dS m ⁻¹)	11.1	0.81
pH	9.0	8.0
K (mg kg ⁻¹)	180	250
P (mg kg ⁻¹)	8.4	11.2
Fe (mg kg ⁻¹)	3.3	6.24
Zn (mg kg ⁻¹)	0.51	0.74
Organic Carbon (SOC) (%)	0.61	0.83
Sand (%)	15	16
Silt (%)	42	58
Clay (%)	43	26
Texture	SiC	SiCL

2.3. The Chemical Properties of Irrigation Water at Experimental Sites

The irrigation water sample was taken and transferred to the laboratory

for chemical analysis. Electrical conductivity (EC) of the irrigation water was measured using an electrical conductivity meter (Jenway model 4310), and pH was determined with a pH

meter (Meterohm 691). Carbonate and bicarbonate were analyzed by titration with sulfuric acid using indicators (phenolphthalein and methyl orange). Calcium and magnesium concentrations

were measured by complexometry, and sodium was determined by direct reading using a flame photometer (Corning M 410). The chemical characteristics of the irrigation water are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. The chemical characteristics of the water used for irrigation at experimental sites

Soil properties	Study sites
EC (mmhos cm ⁻¹)	1.8
pH	7.6
Carbonate (CO ₃ ⁻²) (meq L ⁻¹)	0
Bicarbonate (HCO ₃ ⁻) (meq L ⁻¹)	8.4
Chloride (Cl ⁻) (meq L ⁻¹)	11.1
Calcium (Ca ⁺⁺) (meq L ⁻¹)	4.8
Magnesium (Mg ⁺⁺) (meq L ⁻¹)	5.5
Sodium (Na ⁺) (meq L ⁻¹)	10.8

2.4. Sowing, Cultivation, and Harvesting of Wheat, Experiment Design, and Treatments

The experiment was conducted as a completely randomized block design (CRBD) with three replications over one cropping season at two sites with non-saline and saline soils. The treatments included seven bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) genotypes: the promising lines MS-91-14, MS-89-12, MS-89-13, and the cultivars Ofogh, Mihan, Narin, and Barat. The experiment was conducted at two sites with saline and non-saline soils, each with three replications, at the Miandoab Agricultural Research Station, Iran. The field was irrigated and plowed in early autumn to prepare it for sowing. Sowing was carried out in October using a Wintersteiger seed drill, specifically designed for cereal experiments, in a row planting system. Each plot measured 6 m², consisting of 6 rows, each 5 m in length, with a row spacing of 20 cm. The sowing rate was 450 seeds per m², with a distance of 2 m between replications. Fertilizer application was based on soil analysis results. Urea (46%) was applied at 160 kg ha⁻¹ in three stages: 20 kg ha⁻¹

at field preparation as a basal application, 70 kg ha⁻¹ at tillering, and 70 kg ha⁻¹ at stem elongation. Potassium sulfate (45%) was applied at 80 kg ha⁻¹, and diammonium phosphate at 100 kg ha⁻¹, both at sowing. To ensure uniform emergence and establishment of seedlings, one irrigation was applied immediately after sowing. In mid-April, after favorable environmental conditions, chemical weed control was carried out using the herbicides 2,4-D (2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid) at the recommended rates. From the first week of May, based on local practices and crop water requirements, a total of four additional irrigations were applied until the crop reached full maturity.

2.5. Morphological, Physiological, and Yield-Related Traits of Wheat

The traits evaluated in this study included physiological and agronomic traits, such as leaf chlorophyll content, number of spikes per m², number of spikelets per spike, number of grains per spike, grain weight per spike, and thousand-grain weight, and yield-related traits, including biological yield, grain yield, and harvest index (HI). Grain yield was measured at final harvest using a

cereal combine, harvesting the central portion of each plot while excluding 0.5 m at the beginning and end, and expressed in tons per hectare ($t\ ha^{-1}$). The number of spikelets per spike and the number of grains per spike were measured by counting 10 randomly selected spikes per plot and recording the mean. Grain weight per spike was measured by weighing grains from 10 spikes using a precision balance, and the mean was calculated in grams (g). Thousand-grain weight was determined by counting and weighing 500 grains per plot after harvest. Leaf chlorophyll content was measured using standard procedures with a chlorophyll meter (SPAD502 Plus, Minolta, Japan). After the final harvest, the harvest index (HI) was calculated as the ratio of grain yield to total aboveground biomass (grain yield plus straw, including stalks and chaff).

2.6. Statistical Analysis

After performing the necessary analyses and confirming the normality of the data, analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted based on a completely randomized block design across two soil conditions (locations). Statistical analyses and graph plotting were performed using SPSS and Excel, respectively. Mean comparisons were conducted using Duncan's multiple range test at a 5% probability level ($p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Agronomic and Physiological Traits, Yield Components, and Grain Yield of Wheat

3.1.1. Number of Spikes per m^2

The effects of soil conditions (location), genotype, and soil conditions (locations) \times genotype interaction on the number of spikes per m^2 were significant ($p < 0.05$). Comparison of mean values showed that under non-saline soil conditions, the highest number of spikes per m^2 was observed with an average of 592 spikes per m^2 , while under saline soil conditions, the lowest number was recorded with an average of 302 spikes (Table 3). Among the genotypes and cultivars, cultivar Narin and line MS-89-13 had the highest number of spikes, with averages of 582 and 587 spikes per m^2 , respectively. The Mihan cultivar had the lowest number of spikes per m^2 . Therefore, the genotypes were classified into three distinct statistical groups (Table 3). The highest number of spikes per m^2 was obtained in non-saline soil conditions with cultivars Barat, Narin, and MS-89-13, while the lowest was in saline soil conditions with cultivar Mihan. In all studied genotypes, soil salinity reduced the number of spikes per m^2 . The greatest reduction was observed in cultivar Mihan (52%), while the lowest reduction was found in cultivar Narin (34%) (Figure 1).

Table 3. The mean comparison of yield component traits of wheat genotypes under two different experimental sites

Treatments	Number of spikes per m ²	Spike length (cm)	Number of spikelets per spike	Thousand-grain weight (g)	Number of grains per spike	Spike grain weight
Soil conditions (locations)						
Non-saline soil	592 a	8.7 a*	15.48 a	52.90 a	37.81 a	1.99 a
Saline soil	302 b	8.5 a	15.01 a	43.62 b	34.81 b	1.52 b
Cultivars						
Mihan	296 c	9.50 a	15 abc	49 a	35 c	2.02 ab
Barat	545 a	8.17 bc	15 abc	41 b	27 d	1.22 c
Ofogh	413 b	9.17 ab	17 a	43 b	44 a	2.05 ab
Narin	582 a	8.83 ab	17 a	51 a	38 bc	2.05 ab
Genotypes						
MS-89- 12	302 c	8.17 bc	14 bc	51 a	33 c	1.69 bc
MS-89- 13	587 a	7.33 c	13 c	51 a	25 d	1.37 c
MS-91- 14	403 b	9.33 ab	16 ab	51 a	43 ab	2.24 a

*In each column, the means that have the same letter are not significantly different based on Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% and 1% probability level.

Figure 1. The interaction effect of genotype × soil conditions (location) on the number of spikes per m² in wheat genotypes

3.1.2. Spike Length

The effect of genotype on spike length was significant, while the effects of soil conditions (location) and soil conditions (location) × genotype interaction were not significant at the 5% probability level ($p < 0.05$). Among the studied genotypes, cultivar Mihan, with an average spike length of 9.5 cm, had the longest spikes, while line MS-89-13, with an average of 7.33 cm, had the

shortest. The genotypes were classified into three groups (Table 3). Narjesi et al. (2010) observed that the effect of salinity stress on wheat lines led to a reduction in spike length and spike weight, with the reduction in the evaluated lines (Attila/Kauz) being nearly half compared to the sensitive parent.

3.1.3. The Number of Spikelets Per Spike

The studied genotypes showed statistically significant differences for this trait at the 1% probability level ($p < 0.01$). Among the evaluated genotypes and cultivars, cultivar Narin and Ofogh, with an average of 17 spikelets per spike, had the highest number, while line MS-89-13, with an average of 13 spikelets per spike, had the lowest rate. The genotypes were classified into three groups (Table 3). In this line, Dixit and Chen (2010) stated that the traits of number of spikelets per spike, number of spikes per plant, grain number, grain weight, and grain yield were among the most important traits highly affected by salinity stress, and that salinity stress causes a reduction in these traits.

3.1.4. Thousand-Grain Weight

The effects of soil conditions (locations) and genotypes (and cultivars) on thousand-grain weight were significant at the 1% probability level ($p < 0.01$). Comparison of means showed that under non-saline soil conditions, the genotypes had the highest thousand grain weight with an average of 52.90 g, while under saline soil conditions, they had the lowest with an average of 43.62 g (Table 3). Among the studied genotypes and cultivars, the cultivar Narin and the lines MS-89-12, MS-89-13, and MS-91-14 had the highest thousand-grain weight with an average of 51 g, whereas the cultivar Barat had the lowest with 41 g (Table 3). Likewise, under high salinity conditions, thousand-grain weight

decreases by about 3.7% compared with low salinity levels (Dixit & Chen, 2010).

3.1.5. Number of Grains per Spike

The effects of soil conditions (locations), genotype, and their interaction (soil conditions (locations) \times genotype) on the number of grains per spike were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The mean comparison of values showed that under non-saline soil conditions, the number of grains per spike was highest (37.81 grains per spike), while under saline soil conditions, it was lowest with an average of 34.81 grains per spike (Table 3). Among the studied genotypes, the cultivar Ofogh had the highest number of grains per spike with an average of 44, whereas the line MS-89-13 had the lowest with 25 grains per spike. The genotypes were classified into four groups (Table 3). The highest number of grains per spike under non-saline conditions was observed in line MS-91-14, while the lowest under saline conditions was found in line MS-89-13. In all genotypes except the cultivar Ofogh, soil salinity caused a reduction in the number of grains per spike, with the greatest reduction observed in line MS-89-12 (36%) (Figure 2). The results of Saadatian et al. (2012) indicated that with increasing salinity levels, germination percentage and rate, plant height, thousand grain weight, number of grains per spike, biomass yield, and grain yield of wheat cultivars decreased.

Figure 2. The interaction effect of genotype \times soil conditions (location) on the number of grains per wheat spike.

3.1.6. Spike Grain Weight

The effects of soil conditions (locations), genotype, and genotype \times soil conditions (locations) interaction on spike grain weight were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Mean comparison showed that under non-saline soil conditions, spike grain weight was the highest with an average of 1.99 g, while under saline soil conditions, it was the lowest with an average of 1.52 g (Table 3). Among the examined genotypes and cultivars, line MS-91-14 had the highest spike grain weight with an average of 2.24 g, while the variety Barat had the lowest with an average of 1.22 g. The genotypes were classified into three groups (Table 3). Furthermore, the highest spike grain weight was obtained under non-saline conditions in line MS-91-14, while the lowest values were observed under saline conditions in line

MS-89-13 and the Barat cultivar. In all studied genotypes and cultivars, soil salinity led to a reduction in spike grain weight, with the highest reduction (45%) observed in line MS-89-12 (Figure 3). Mahdi Nezhad et al. (2015) also reported that salinity stress reduced the number of spikes per unit area, number of grains per spike, and grain weight in Recombinant Inbred Lines (RILs) of wheat. Salinity stress has been shown to significantly reduce wheat productivity by influencing key agronomic traits. Grain weight had also been identified as the most decisive yield component under salinity conditions, outweighing the contribution of other yield traits (Saberi et al., 2013). In agreement, salinity stress had been reported to cause notable decreases in both grain yield and grain weight per spike (Narjesi et al., 2010).

Figure 3. The interaction effect of genotype × soil conditions (locations) on the spike grain weight of wheat genotypes

3.1.7. Chlorophyll Content

Based on the results of the analysis of variance, both the location and wheat genotypes had significant effects on chlorophyll content ($p < 0.01$). The non-saline soil, with a mean of 53 units, showed higher chlorophyll content compared with the saline soil, which had a mean of 41 units (Table 4). Among the genotypes, line MS-91-14 had the highest chlorophyll content with a mean of 59 units, while the cultivar Mihan had the lowest with a mean of 40 units (Table 4). Mihan is considered a salt-sensitive cultivar, which explains its lowest chlorophyll content. Salender Kumar et al. (2003) reported that chlorophyll

degradation occurs less in more salt-tolerant cultivars. According to the analysis of variance, no statistically significant interaction was observed between soil condition and genotype for chlorophyll content. Another detrimental effect of increased salinity is the acceleration of leaf senescence, which results from the reduction in chlorophyll content under salt stress. de Lacerda et al. (2003); Kaya et al. (2001); Kaya et al. (2002) found that salinity reduces chlorophyll concentration. Lutts et al. (1996), in an experiment on rice plants, observed that the reduction in chlorophyll concentration due to salinity was also greater in older leaves.

Table 4. Comparison of mean values of agronomic and physiological traits in wheat genotypes across two experimental locations

Treatments	chlorophyll content	Biomass yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Harvest Index (HI)
Soil conditions (locations)				
Non-saline soil	53 a	13286 a	6539 a	49.06 a
Saline soil	41 b	7017 b	2821 b	40.38 b
Cultivars				
Mihan	40 d	7000 e	3200 b	47 b
Barat	55 ab	8500 de	3720 b	43 cd
Ofogh	48 c	9500 cd	4153 b	42 d
Narin	48.50 c	13000 a	6313 a	46 bc
Genotypes				
MS-89- 12	51 bc	9000 cde	3907 b	42 cd
MS-89- 13	51 bc	11000 bc	5660 a	51 a
MS-91- 14	59 a	12500 ab	5613 a	43 cd

*In each column, the means that have the same letter are not significantly different based on Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% and 1% probability level.

3.1.8. Biological Yield

The effects of soil condition (locations), genotype, and the soil conditions (locations) × genotype interaction on biological yield were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Comparison of mean values indicated that under non-saline soil conditions, biological yield was highest with an average of 13286 kg ha⁻¹, while under saline soil conditions, it was lowest (7017 kg ha⁻¹) (Table 4). Among the genotypes and cultivars, the Narin variety had the highest biomass yield with 13000 kg ha⁻¹, and the Mihan variety had the lowest with an average of 7000 kg ha⁻¹. The genotypes were grouped into four categories. The highest biological yield under non-saline

conditions was observed in line MS-91-14, and the lowest under saline conditions was observed in the Mihan cultivar. In all genotypes studied, soil salinity caused a reduction in this trait, with the greatest reduction observed in line MS-91-14 at over 50% (Figure 4). Narjesi et al. (2010) investigated the effect of salinity stress on grain yield and plant traits of pure recombinant wheat lines and found that salinity stress affected all vegetative and reproductive traits of wheat. In the control experiment, grain yield was twice as high as under salinity stress, and biomass weight in the control was three times greater than under stress. Similar results have been reported by Munns and James (2003).

Figure 4. The interaction effect of genotype × soil conditions (location) on the biological yield of wheat genotypes

3.1.9. Grain Yield

The effects of soil condition (locations), genotype, and the soil conditions (locations) × genotype interaction on grain yield were statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). The mean comparison of values showed that under non-saline soil conditions, grain yield was highest with an average of 6539 kg ha⁻¹, while under saline soil conditions, it was lowest with an average of 2821 kg ha⁻¹ (Table 4). Among the genotypes and cultivars, the Narin cultivar had the highest grain yield with 6313 kg ha⁻¹, and the Mihan cultivar had the lowest with an average of 3200 kg ha⁻¹. The genotypes were grouped into two categories. Thalji and Shalalkeh (2007) screened wheat and barley genotypes for salinity tolerance by growing 10 bread wheat genotypes, 12 durum wheat genotypes, and 11 barley genotypes

under salinity levels of 20.6–21.9 dS m⁻¹ and 4.5–5.5 dS m⁻¹. They reported that different wheat and barley genotypes showed significant differences in biological efficiency and grain yield. The highest grain yield under non-saline conditions was observed in line MS-91-14, while the lowest under saline conditions was observed in the Mihan cultivar. In all genotypes studied, soil salinity reduced grain yield, with the greatest reduction observed in line MS-91-14, exceeding 50% (Figure 5). El-Hendawy et al. (2005), by evaluating numerous wheat cultivars using cluster analysis, reported that salinity stress often reduces wheat yield potential by decreasing the number of fertile tillers. Similarly, Noori et al. (2006) reported that grain yield reduction in wheat under salinity stress is due to the impact on yield components.

Figure 5. The interaction effect of genotype × soil conditions (location) on the grain yield of wheat genotypes

3.1.10. Harvest Index

The effects of soil conditions (locations), genotype, and cultivars on grain yield were statistically significant for the harvest index trait ($p < 0.05$). In non-saline conditions, with an average of 49.06%, the harvest index was higher compared to saline conditions, with an average of 40.28% (Table 4). Accordingly, genotype MS-89-13, with an average of 51%, had the highest harvest index, while cultivar Ofogh, with an average of 42%, had the lowest (Table 4). The analysis of variance also indicated that there was no statistically significant interaction effect between the studied soil conditions (locations) and genotypes for the harvest index trait.

3.2. Simple Correlation Between Studied Traits under Non-Saline Soil Conditions

The correlation between grain yield and thousand-grain weight was positive and significant ($r = 0.563^*$) (Table 5). In addition, the correlation between grain yield and biological yield was positive but not significant ($r = 0.343$), indicating that the selection of

genotypes with higher biological yield was not of great importance in the absence of stress. In other words, in wheat genotypes, greater vegetative growth and biomass production did not necessarily result in higher grain yield. The correlation between grain yield and harvest index was positive and significant ($r = 0.618^*$). This suggested that one of the most important traits for selecting genotypes with high grain yield was a high harvest index, meaning that genotypes that allocate a greater proportion of their biomass to grain production were more favorable. Among the studied traits, grain yield had the highest positive and significant correlation with the number of spikes per m^2 . This indicated that spike numbers were a key determinant of grain yield under non-stress conditions. Similarly, Emam et al. (2007) reported, in their evaluation of grain yield and its components in wheat genotypes, a significant positive correlation between grain yield and both the number of grains per spike and biological yield under non-stress conditions.

Table 5. Correlation coefficients of studied traits under non-soil salinity conditions

Traits	Biological Yield	Spike grain weight	No. of spikes per m ²	No. of grains per Spike	No. of spikelets per spike	Grain Yield	1000-grain yield	Harvest Index
Biological Yield	1							
Spike grain weight	0.382	1						
No. of spikes per m ²	0.367	-0.135	1					
No. of grains per Spike	0.203	0.860**	0.180	1				
No. of spikelets per spike	0.398	0.090	0.068	0.881**	1			
Grain Yield	0.343	0.394	0.896**	0.346	0.191	1		
1000-grain yield	0.476*	0.364	0.276	-0.223	-0.218	0.563*	1	
Harvest Index	0.322	0.237	0.339	0.301	0.312	0.618*	0.661*	1

*and ** are significant at the 5% and 1% probability levels, respectively.

3.3. Simple Correlation Between Studied Traits Under Soil Salinity

According to Table 6, under saline conditions, the correlation between grain yield and biological yield ($r=0.544^*$) and thousand-grain weight ($r=0.763^{**}$) was positive and significant. The positive and significant correlation between grain yield and biomass yield indicated that under soil salinity stress, selecting genotypes with higher biomass yield was important, as higher biomass contributes significantly to higher grain yield. The negative correlation between the number of grains per spike and thousand-grain weight ($r=-0.321$) and the positive and significant correlation between grain yield and thousand-grain

weight ($r=0.763^{**}$), along with the lack of significant correlation between grain yield and number of grains per spike ($r=0.301$), indicated that under soil saline stress, grain weight was more important in determining grain yield. Salehi and Mosavat (2012) cultivated 22 wheat genotypes along with three reference wheat varieties (Zagros, Kavir, and the promising line of No. 4) in saline and non-saline areas. Based on simple and combined analyses across the two soil conditions, they reported significant differences among genotypes. They also found a significant correlation between harvest index and thousand-grain weight with yield under saline conditions.

Table 6. Correlation coefficients of studied traits under soil salinity conditions

Traits	Biological Yield	Spike grain weight	No. of spikes per m ²	No. of grains per Spike	No. of spikelets per spike	Grain Yield	1000-grain yield
Spike grain weight	0.291	1					
No. of spikes per m ²	0.827**	-0.135	1				
No. of grains per Spike	0.154	0.980**	0.290	1			
No. of spikelets per spike	0.380	-0.090	0.068	0.942**	1		
Grain Yield	0.544*	0.794**	0.696*	0.301	0.207	1	
1000-grain yield	0.476*	0.314	0.176	-0.321	-0.318	0.763**	1
Harvest Index	0.221	0.537*	0.312	0.101	0.202	0.598*	0.581*

*and ** are significant at the 5% and 1% probability levels, respectively.

4. Conclusion

Based on the evaluations and observations of agronomic and

physiological traits affecting grain yield in seven bread wheat genotypes and cultivars across two soil conditions

(locations), significant differences were observed between the two locations and among the wheat genotypes and cultivars for all studied traits. The comparison of mean values for grain yield components indicated that among all genotypes and cultivars, the Barat cultivar had the lowest spike weight and thousand-grain weight. Furthermore, the high grain yield of the Narin cultivar could be attributed to its higher thousand-grain weight, number of spikelets per spike, number of spikes per m², and biomass yield. In addition, based on the mean grain yield under soil saline stress, the Mihan cultivar, with a lower grain yield, was identified as a sensitive cultivar to soil salinity stress. Overall, the Narin genotype showed the highest grain yield, harvest index, and biomass yield under soil salinity stress and could be considered a soil salinity-tolerant cultivar in the West Azerbaijan province of Iran. The MS-89-13 genotype was also identified as a soil salinity-tolerant wheat genotype in this study. Therefore, Narin cultivar and MS-89-13 genotype can be recommended for cultivation in saline soils to achieve higher grain yield in the West Azerbaijan province of Iran.

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